

RESEARCH OF INTERNAL AND EXTERNAL MARKETING ENVIRONMENT OF TEXTILE ENTERPRISES OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: In 2017-2022, Uzbekistan adopted a new version of a number of laws in the field of economy. All the adopted laws in the new version allow business entities to work on the basis of the real market mechanism. Similarly, extensive economic reforms have dramatically changed the environment for textile enterprises. Today, textile enterprises operate in a rapidly changing market environment. Based on this, this article researches the internal and external marketing environment of textile enterprises of Uzbekistan. Factors affecting the internal and external environment of textile enterprises were determined and the level of impact was evaluated.

Keywords: light industry, textile enterprises, internal marketing environment, external marketing environment, marketing strategy, market share, STEP analysis.

Introduction

For many years, Uzbekistan exported only cotton fiber. Today, the country occupies a place in the world textile market not only as a supplier of cotton fiber, but also as an exporter of textile products, especially finished products.

The introduction of new production technologies in the textile industry, the use of highly efficient, modern equipment, and at the same time effective management ensure high labor efficiency and an increase in the volume of industrial production.

It should be mentioned that the light industry, being a strategic sector for the economy of Uzbekistan, provides a high level of employment and contributes to the increase of economic and industrial potential.

Sustainable development of the national economy of Uzbekistan, ensuring economic growth, modernization of industries and production complexes providing consumer goods production, diversification of production taking into account market changes are defined as priority goals in the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026.

As one of the most important multi-sectoral sectors of the economy, light industry has a high level of investment attractiveness and innovative development. This affects the development of the network and the economic growth of the country.

In general, as a result of the economic reforms carried out in Uzbekistan in the last 5-6 years, the environment in the market of textile products is changing dramatically. Only since April 2020, the European Union system of preferences for sustainable development and governance (GSP+) has entered into force for Uzbekistan. This ensures that the textile products of Uzbekistan enter the European market.

Such technical-technological, economic, political changes require textile enterprises to research the internal and external marketing environment. Based on this, the methodological

aspects of researching the internal and external marketing environment of textile enterprises were studied in detail in this article.

Literature analysis on the topic

The study of the marketing environment, the factors affecting it, the components of internal and external environmental factors, as well as the theoretical aspects of the study of the influence of factors were widely studied in the works of F. Kotler, a leading specialist in marketing [8]. The main stages of strategic marketing planning are the research of the internal and external marketing environment, the issues of marketing planning based on the situation in the environment Mac-Donald M. reflected in his works [10].

The scientific-theoretical basis of the analysis of internal and external environments in marketing activities is also widely studied in the research of Assel Henry [1]. It is in textile enterprises that there are specialists who have studied the issues of the marketing environment. In particular, issues of the marketing environment in the development of export of textile products Dodeltseva N.V. [6] and N.K. Temnova [11] were widely studied.

The researches of Uzbek scientists within the analyzed topic are also of special importance. In particular, the research conducted by A.Sh.Bekmuradov [2] and M.R.Boltaboev [3], who are considered leaders among Uzbek marketing scientists, within the framework of marketing strategies for the development of the textile industry, is commendable. Young specialists O. Davronov [5] and G. Zakhidov. [7] He is conducting extensive research on the development of the textile industry, the role of clusters, and increasing the economic potential of textile enterprises.

Research methodology

The method of expert survey was used in researching the internal and external marketing environment of textile enterprises of Uzbekistan. Based on the expert survey, the factors affecting the internal and external environment of enterprises operating in Uzbekistan were determined. A weight coefficient was assigned to each factor, and the level of influence on marketing efficiency was evaluated. Also, in the study, the state of the internal environment of textile enterprises and the threats of the external environment were determined using economic-statistical analysis, STEP analysis, and monographic observation methods.

Analysis and results

The volume of production of textile products in Uzbekistan is increasing in recent years as a result of the establishment of clusters and the introduction of innovative technologies in the field. In particular, the production of textile products makes up more than 14.0 percent of the manufacturing industry. 62757.0 billion in 2022. Soum textile products were produced (Table 1).

Table 1

Dynamics of the production volume of textile products and clothing in 2018-2022 (billion soums)*

Indicators	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Production of textile products	24835,1	31726,3	40864,5	52372,3	62757,0
Clothing production	11367,2	9648,4	10167,3	13592,8	17210,1

* source. Author's development based on the information of the association "Uztoqimachilik sanoat".

As can be seen from Table 1, the production of textile products in 2022 compared to 2021 will be 10384.7 billion. soums (119.8%) and clothing production 3617.3 bln. increased by soums (126.6%). Regions with the highest share in the total volume of products produced by textile enterprises on a national scale:

Fergana region - 14.6%;

Tashkent region - 10.2%;

Kashkadarya region - 9.2%;

Samarkand region - 9.1%.

The production of textile products is becoming the main part of the country's manufacturing industry. In 2022, 14.6 percent of the manufacturing industry was textile production (Table 2).

Table 2

The share of textile and clothing production in the manufacturing industry in 2018-2022 *, %

Indicators	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Manufacturing industry	100	100	100	100	100
Production of textile products	13,1	11,8	12,0	13,8	14,6
Clothing production	4,1	3,6	3,4	3,6	3,9

* **source. Author's development based on the information of the association "Uztoqimachilik sanoat".**

The measures taken in the direction of the development of the industry made it possible to attract serious investments in the modernization and technological upgrading of the production base, the purchase of the latest equipment for the deep processing of cotton by textile enterprises and clusters, and the production of ready-made textile products according to international standards.

At present, the analysis of the situation in the successful development of the textile industry of Uzbekistan, the study of the internal and external marketing environment are considered urgent issues.

The technological features of textile enterprises allow to quickly change the range of products with minimal costs. This ensures high mobility of production.

Enterprises operating in the textile sector operate under the influence of constantly changing internal relations, as well as relations between them and other economic entities. The sum of active entities and their forces that influence the strategy of textile enterprises externally and internally forms the marketing environment. The marketing environment often defines the description of the company's activities - therefore, in the organization of marketing research, great attention is paid to the study of the internal and external environment.

The internal environment is part of the overall marketing environment that is within and controlled by the enterprise. It consists of several components, each of which consists of a set of enterprise elements and key processes. The state of internal marketing of textile enterprises determines the potential of the enterprise. Enterprise potential is the complex capabilities that ensure competition and achievement of results in market conditions.

In the analysis of the internal marketing situation of textile enterprises, it is necessary to pay attention to the following: the effectiveness of the used marketing strategies; the status of manufactured products and their place in the market; market share distribution of enterprises; state of production forces, equipment, research and innovation; the degree of development of relations between suppliers of enterprise goods, relations between them, and buyers; level of provision of material, technical and financial resources; the company's position in relation to its competitors; connection with the external environment; the image of the enterprise and its products; the interest of the company's employees for the success of the company's activities; the goals of employees, their skills and their full use, etc.

The main goal of analyzing the state of internal marketing of textile enterprises is to study the factors that determine and influence the potential of the enterprise. For this, it is necessary to focus on the following factors:

Management: management organization structure, division of labor, control of decision implementation, management information system, communication processes, type of management, professional nature and level of senior management, strategic planning system.

Production: production departments (number, specialists, capacity), the volume of products that are rented or produced depending on the current state of its own production base, the type of technology used, product quality control, security, production force, direct involvement in product production proper losses. It is also important to assess the level of full utilization of production capacity.

Marketing: applied strategies, market (large-small, position, competitors), customers, corporate image, brand, price, sales and communication policy, information supply status and organization, relationship marketing, internal marketing. One of the important areas of modern analysis is benchmarking - methods of evaluating one's own marketing activities in relation to companies that are considered as benchmarks.

Financial and economic potential: enterprise assets, own and borrowed capital, credit facilities, capital turnover rate and liquidity, capital planning, gross income, profit and its use. One of the important indicators of enterprise activity is its profitability. It is calculated based on the ratio of the received income indicator (sales volume, gross income, working capital to production, cost of fixed assets, etc.).

Employees (personnel) - composition and qualification, professional and qualification level, personnel formation policy (planning, selection and temporary hiring, dismissal, unemployment, etc.), personnel development (professional orientation and retraining, certification and evaluation, service ensuring its growth in the process), organization and promotion of work, etc.

The analysis of the external marketing situation in textile enterprises is a unity of two systems that develop independently of each other: the meso-environment and the macro-environment.

The macro environment creates general conditions for enterprise activity. It forms the forces and factors affecting the market as a whole, and at the same time affecting each entity individually.

In most cases, macro-environmental factors will not have a specific description for a particular enterprise. But each of them feels its influence and cannot control it. You can only adapt to the macro environment. Each enterprise independently solves the issues of adaptation, trying to strengthen its positive impact and reduce the consequences of negative impact. The study of the macroenvironment requires the analysis of its constituent factors. These factors are: demographic, economic, natural, social-cultural, scientific-technical, political-legal.

In the analysis of the internal marketing situation of textile enterprises, the export performance of enterprises is also important. In 2022, all the enterprises operating within the "Uztoqiliksanoat" association exported finished textile products worth 1.2 billion US dollars. At the moment, the enterprises of the "Uztoqimaliksanoat" association are exporting their products to Russia, Turkey, Canada, South Korea, Singapore, Iran, Israel, the CIS countries, the PRC, the USA and a number of Arab countries, and the export potential of the enterprises within the association is growing year by year.

A number of changes are also taking place in the structure of export of textile products. In particular, the export of finished textile products is increasing year by year, while the export of yarn is decreasing (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Structural changes in the export of textile products, forecast indicators for 2030 *

* source. Author's development based on the information of the association "Uztoqimachilikanoat".

An important process in the analysis of the state of internal marketing is the study of factors affecting the activity of enterprises. When assessing the level of influence of factors, it is appropriate to create a specialization matrix (Table 3). In it, each factor is given an expert assessment according to the following indicators: importance for the network (high - 3 points, average - 2 points, low - 1 point); impact on the enterprise (strong - 3 points, average - 2 points, weak - 1 point, no impact - 0 points); direction of influence (positive +1, negative -1). Integral assessment (D) is created from the multiplication of expert assessments.

Table 3

Specialization matrix to be formed in the research of the internal marketing situation of textile enterprises

Internal marketing situation factors	Importance to the network (A)	Impact on the enterprise (B)	Direction of influence (C)	Level of importance (D = A+BC)
Opportunities to increase production capacity	2	3	+1	5
Equipment of production equipment, production tools with modern brands	2	2	+1	4
Direct losses in product production	2	2	-1	4
Opportunities to improve product quality	3	2	+1	5
Having top management	3	3	+1	6
Growth rate of sales turnover	2	3	+1	5
Availability of high value fixed assets	2	2	+1	4
Sufficient number of qualified professionals	2	2	+1	4
The strength of the marketing strategy	3	3	+1	6

The main purpose of expert evaluations is to evaluate the marketing efficiency of business entities. The multi-factor evaluation method for determining the effectiveness of marketing proposed for use in the research work includes the following steps in textile enterprises:

1. Evaluation of the influence of internal and external environmental factors based on the results of an expert survey in order to analyze the marketing activity of the enterprise.
2. Analytical assessment based on conceptual and logical models of the subject area of increasing marketing efficiency of enterprises.
3. Formation of an information-analytical system of marketing effectiveness assessment for management decision-making.

Based on the results of the internal and external marketing situation analysis, a matrix of solutions is created, in which there are four possible solutions:

- external opportunities - internal strengths of the enterprise;
- external opportunities - internal weaknesses of the enterprise;
- external threats - internal strengths of the enterprise;
- external threats are a combination of internal strengths of the enterprise.

Consequently, the highest threat (or opportunity) is rated with 9 points; a threat or opportunity of medium strength is evaluated with 6 points, a threat or opportunity of low

strength is estimated with 2 points. After extracting the factors considered as the highest level of threats and opportunities for the company's activity, it is transferred to the STEP-analysis.

STEP-analysis procedure:

1. External strategic factors with a high (probability) level of occurrence and impact on the enterprise's activities are identified. The degree of influence of each event-factor on the company's strategy is evaluated: "5" - has a strong influence, "1" - does not have an influence. In this case, 5 points, 6-4 points, 4-3 points, 2-2 points, 1-1 points are given to factors with an integral evaluation of 9 points in the specialization matrix of the microenvironment.
2. The importance (probability) of each event is assessed by giving it a specific weight (from 0 to 1). In this case, the sum of all weights should be equal to 1.
3. By multiplying the influence of each factor by its importance (weight of the factor), a relative (comparative) assessment is given to it.
4. General relative (comparative) assessment of threats is determined.
5. A general relative (comparative) assessment of capabilities is determined.
6. By determining the ratio of the overall relative (comparative) assessment of opportunities to the overall relative (comparative) assessment of threats, the level of readiness of the enterprise to respond to existing and predictable factors is determined.

Determining weight coefficients is one of the important problems in the implementation of strategic analysis. The weight coefficient expresses the tendency of increasing or decreasing the influence of one or another factor on the enterprise's activity. Thus, the forecast of the development of the situation in the textile industry is reflected in the weight coefficient.

Methodology (style) of calculating weight coefficients:

1. All factors that need to be determined by the weighting factor are separated.
2. Each factor is given a certain color depending on the level of forecasting its importance: "5" - the probability of the occurrence of the event is high (the factor has a tendency to increase its influence), "1" - the probability of the occurrence of the event is low.
3. The sum of all factor colors is determined.
4. The weight coefficient is determined by dividing the factor color by the total sum of all colors.
5. The sum of all weighting coefficients must be equal to one.

The calculation of the weight coefficients is shown in Table 4, and the color given to one or another factor reflects the forecast of its importance increasing or decreasing over time.

Table 4

Determination of weight coefficients

External strategic factors	Color (factor importance)	Weighting coefficients
High level of technological changes and innovative activity in the textile industry	5	$5/39 = 0,128$
Support of investment attraction projects	5	$5/39 = 0,128$
State support of the processing industry	3	$3/39 = 0,077$
Employment dynamics	2	$2/39 = 0,051$
Increase in the current income of the population	4	$4/39 = 0,103$

Changes in the standard of living of the population	3	$3/39 = 0,077$
Impact of environmental changes on enterprise activity	4	$4/39 = 0,103$
Development of suppliers, intermediaries and logistics companies	5	$5/39 = 0,128$
Demographic changes	3	$3/39 = 0,077$
Impact of inflation on business activity	5	$5/39 = 0,128$
The sum of the colors	39	
Sum of weighting coefficients		1,0

Here it is appropriate to mention some comments: assigning one or another color depends on the level of importance of the considered factor. In the above example, "Effects of environmental changes on enterprise activity" is considered as a threat and represents a sharp decrease in the production volume of the enterprises with the highest color. If this factor was considered as an opportunity, giving it the highest color would mean that the production capacity of enterprises would increase.

A list of strategic external factors affecting the textile industry, as well as external strategic factors affecting the performance of each studied entity, is presented in Table 4. The level of influence of external strategic factors was evaluated. Sum of weighting coefficients.

The external environment can be affected by extreme changes. Therefore, at the stage of preliminary analysis of the environment and assessment of its impact on the enterprise, it is necessary to take into account the development of events in at least the following three directions: realistic development of events (taking into account the current situation), pessimistic development of events (the environment has the highest negative impact on the enterprise); optimistic development of events (changes in the environment will have a positive effect on the company's activities). For this reason, it is necessary to draw up three tables for evaluating the impact of environmental factors, taking into account three options for the development of events.

Table 6 shows the relative assessment of the impact of environmental factors on enterprise activity.

Table 6

Relative assessment of the influence of environmental factors

External strategic factors	Weight	Grade	Relative value
Opportunities			
High level of technological changes and innovative activity in the textile industry	0,128	5	0,64
Support of investment attraction projects	0,128	5	0,64
State support of the processing industry	0,077	3	0,231
Increase in the current income of the population	0,103	4	0,412

Changes in the standard of living of the population	0,077	3	0,231
Development of suppliers, intermediaries and logistics companies	0,128	5	0,64
			2,794
Threats			
Employment dynamics	0,051	2	0,102
Impact of environmental changes on enterprise activity	0,103	4	0,412
Demographic changes	0,077	3	0,231
			0,745

After identifying the opportunities and threats from the analysis of the internal and external marketing situation, the internal marketing situation of the enterprise is analyzed through the following five parameters:

1. Effectiveness of the (current) strategy used by the enterprise.
2. Determination of resource potential, strengths and weaknesses of the enterprise.
3. Competitiveness of the enterprise in terms of price and costs.
4. Stability of a significant (main) competitive position in comparison with the main competitors.
5. Strategic problems of the enterprise.

The expert method was also used to assess the internal and external environment of enterprises. At the first stage, a survey of established experts was carried out. Leading specialists of 14 "Uztogamiliksanoat" associations, marketing, sales, logistics, and production managers of enterprises producing a wide range of products were selected as experts. The possible statistical error of the data was 2.95%.

Data processing and interpretation were performed by analyzing interval distributions and interface tables in Excel layouts.

During the analysis of the results of the expert survey, the internal and external factors preventing the improvement of the marketing efficiency of the textile enterprises of Uzbekistan were determined. The composition of identified factors was also compiled by experts. That is, the list of factors affecting the marketing efficiency of textile enterprises was first formed. Then a survey of experts on the influence of factors was carried out (Table 7).

Table 7

Internal factors affecting the marketing efficiency of textile enterprises of Uzbekistan

Answer options	Percentage of respondents, %
Failure to develop a marketing plan for each market segment	32
Failure to regularly conduct marketing research on market conditions, market capacity, market share, consumer behavior, competitor studies	16
Lack of development of clear marketing strategies	14
Low position of the enterprise brand in the market	12
Low utilization of opportunities to enter new sales markets and	11

diversify the product range	
Lack of qualified marketing professionals	9
Others	6

source: Author's calculation based on expert assessment

Conclusion

Based on a survey of experts, the most important place among the internal factors affecting marketing efficiency is related to the strategic planning of marketing activities. The lack of development of a clear marketing plan and marketing programs affects the effectiveness of working with the target market, ensuring competitive advantage. Also, lack of regular marketing research on market conditions, market capacity, market share, consumer behavior, competitor studies is affecting all other aspects of marketing activities.

The effectiveness of the (current) strategy used by the enterprise is based on the main indicators describing the stability of the textile products market (compliance with accreditation indicators in the main areas of activity, attracting extra-budgetary sources of financing, the ability to attract new ones while retaining old consumers, the reputation of the enterprise in front of consumers, production techniques, innovations, quality of textile products, price level, potential opportunities for opening required specializations) are determined.

When assessing the resource potential of the enterprise, it is considered as a system consisting of subsystems that perform management, production capacity, level of investment attraction, economic, marketing and economic activities. Identifying the strengths and weaknesses of each sub-system is the basis for developing functional strategies..

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